
VISUAL ORGANIZERS AS SCAFFOLDING TECHNIQUES IN TEACHING ENGLISH IN NONPHILOLOGICAL UNIVERSITIES

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Abstract: This article is devoted to the methods of teaching a foreign language in non-philological higher education institutions and the problems of language learning. In addition, the article describes the effectiveness of using visual aids.

Keywords: Visualization, language, method, skill, technology.

Наглядные пособие как техника скаффолдинга в преподавании английского языка в нефилологических вузах

Аннотация: Данная статья посвящена методам преподавания иностранного языка в нефилологических высших учебных заведениях и проблемам изучения языка. Кроме того, в статье рассказывается об эффективности использования наглядных пособий.

Ключевые слова: Визуализация, язык, метод, навык, технология.

Nofilologik Oliy ta'lim yo'nalishlarida ingliz tilini o'qitishda skaffolding texnikasi sifatida ko'rgazmali qurollardan foydalanish.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqola nofilologik oliy ta'lim muassasalarida chet tilini o'qitish usullarini va til o'rganishdagi qiyinchiliklarga bag'ishlangan. Bundan tashqari, maqolada, ko'rgazmali qurollardan foydalanish samaradorligini haqida gapiriladi.

Kalit so'zlar: ko'rgazmali qurollar, til, usul, mahorat, texnologiya.

Using visual organizers in ESP classes can establish a strong communicative setting where children are encouraged to learn English interactively. It's outdated to dismiss the benefits of visual aids in teaching these classes. This thesis answers four key questions, based on research, to highlight the effectiveness of visual organizers in EFL classrooms: 1. What are visual organizers and do they impact an EFL classroom? 2. How do visual organizers foster a social and communicative atmosphere in an EFL classroom? 3. How do visual organizers motivate children? 4. How should a teacher incorporate visual organizers in teaching EFL?

Review of Literature. What Is the Definition of a Visual Organizer and Do Visual Inputs Matter in an ESP Classroom? Since the mid-twentieth century, the world has been marked by the global expansion of communications media and a burgeoning visual culture, radically altering the dissemination and production of information and knowledge. Education, widely espoused as the principal instrument of social change, is fundamentally challenged and transfigured by this process. Visual media culture was perceived as having an overwhelming impact on conventional literacy and pedagogy but also touted as a potentially powerful tool for educators (Goldfarb, 2002). Dierking further makes critical comments regarding Goldfarb's viewpoint: "what is unique is Goldfarb's suggestion that the revolution is fundamentally transforming-and at that same time challenging-our notions of education, and I would argue, learning" (Dierking, 2003, pp. 343-344). In 1983, Gardner suggested that people are born with at least seven intelligences, standing for a "broad range of human abilities" that can be seen "working in their lives in a variety of ways ...given a context-rich and naturalistic setting" (Boiarsky, 1997, pp. 11-12). He categorized this intelligence as follows: "Linguistic Intelligence; Logical-Mathematical Intelligence; Spatial Intelligence; Bodily-Kinesthetic Intelligence; Musical Intelligence; Interpersonal Visual Organizers As Scaffolds... 6 Intelligence; Intrapersonal Intelligence; Naturalist Intelligence" (Armstrong, 2000, pp.2-3). A decade later, in 1994, Armstrong, who works as an educator and psychologist in the fields of multiple intelligences,

explains that a person's learning style is "the intelligence put to work...learning styles are the pragmatic manifestation of intelligence operating in natural learning contexts" (1994, p. 13). Furthermore, based on the theory of "Multiple Intelligences", he proposes the theory of "Seven kinds of smart" along with a publication with the same title. It endows learners, no matter in schools or in workplaces, to identify one's multiple intelligences. As well, it provides practical exercises and tips for developing them, and ideas on using one's intelligence to overcome learning difficulties, enhance relationships, and improve learning satisfaction. Armstrong further argues that teachers or students do not have to teach or learn something in all seven ways, just see what the possibilities are, and then decide which particular pathways interest the most, or seem to be the most effective teaching/learning tools. This theory is so intriguing because it expands the horizon of available teaching/learning tools Visual Organizers As Scaffolds... 7 beyond the conventional linguistic and logical methods used in most schools. For example, lectures, textbooks, writing assignments, and formulas. In detail, Gardner states that spatial intelligence is the ability to perceive the visual-spatial world accurately and to transform those perceptions. It involves the potential to recognize and use spatial and visual patterns within more confined areas. As well, Armstrong states that the "Spatial Intelligence" has the capacity "to examine a graphic chart that illustrates the principle" and to derive meaning out of it. He labels it as "picture smart," a more direct and clarified definition. That is the reason for centuries why the application of visual aids in teaching and learning styles in various domains has been keeping influential. The emphasis of Comenius regarding the "principles for teachers" states that "use objects or pictures to illustrate concepts" which is the strong proof of Gardner's discovery. It is undeniable that every individual learner has different superior intelligences. In addition, not every individual learner acquires knowledge through the same process. However, countless teachers still insist their own traditional instructing methods and materials, and lead the learning style which they believe is right and

better. In the West, in the foreign language learning classrooms, meaningful inputs are provided by the great support from visual aids. Grittner addresses these principles regarding foreign language teaching based on psychological studies Visual Organizers As Scaffolds... 8 (Appendix B). It is critical for language learners to have something to look at that is eye-catching and attention-keeping as well as relevant to the task in hand (Wright & Haleem, 1991). Simply, it is called a visual organizer or visual aid – a visual or graphic means of organizing written materials (Graves, 1994). From an educational perspective, it is an instructional aid, such as a poster, scale model, or videotape that presents information visually. More specifically, “Visual organizers are visual frameworks such as figures, diagrams, charts, etc. used to present structural knowledge spatially in a given area to enhance comprehension and learning” (Shumin, 2004, pp. 58-66). In addition, Walker, who is an advocate for visual education in early grades explains that “Visual organizers (also called thinking tools, graphic organizers, or key visuals) are formats for organizing information and ideas graphically. They use words, pictures, and graphic cues to help students to generate ideas, record and reorganize information, and see relationships” (Walker, 2004. p. 39). This thesis is not discussing the specific visual inputs used to help a particular group – “visual learners,” whose learning is achieved most easily when information is conveyed through visual cues. Further, they cannot even learn something until have seen it (Lightbown & Spada, 2004, p. 58). On the contrary, this thesis promotes the fact that using visual organizers as Scaffolds... 9 scaffolds for teaching general learners in ESP classrooms to enhance their development of English language competencies.

Conclusion From the above analysis, a conclusion can be drawn that teaching and learning English by means of language visualization effective and efficient in improving students` communicative ability. While in the traditional method of teaching English, Images, graphs, and diagrams are some of the most

effective scaffolding tools. These visual aids help students organize new information, understand abstract concepts, and recall content for the next lesson. Visuals can significantly improve student performance in everyday tasks such as group discussions, essay writing, and handling handouts.

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